

AN ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF THE YOLO ALGORITHM IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF BLOOD CELL IMAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10723507>

Abstract. *Peripheral smear is a method that allows the analysis of blood with the help of a microscope after staining the blood liquid on a glass slide. The morphological appearance and multiplicity of some blood elements are examined by this method. This examination is preferred for evaluating the response to treatment as well as providing information about the diagnosis and severity of diseases. Since manual examination of blood elements by operators contains many humanistic and environmental parameters, it is time-consuming and error-prone. Instead of this approach which does not offer a standard accuracy rate, it is planned to create a quick, cost-effective and fully automatic computer-aided system. In this study, the examination of ALL (Acute Lymphoblastic Leukaemia) malignancy which is one of the main types of leukaemia by peripheral smear method will be handled*

Keywords: *X-ray films, Machine Learning, diagnosis, performance, algorithms, differentia, dental panoramic.*

Introduction Acute lymphoblastic leukaemia is a hematic disorder known as cancer of the white blood cells. It is occurred by the excessive production of malignant and immature white blood cells known as lymphoblast or blast produced in the bone marrow. This malignancy, which generally affects young children and adults over 50, spreads rapidly to the bloodstream and vital organs. Therefore, early diagnosis is the basic principle for the sustainability of vitality.

In the first stage of ALL cancer, general symptoms such as weakness, weight loss, loss of appetite, nosebleeds, bone or joint pains and shortness of breath are observed. However, in the later stages, blast cells that are overproduced in the bone marrow begin to be seen in the peripheral blood. Evaluation of peripheral blood film is part of the diagnostic process.

This study is planned to perform the analysis of blood cells in a fast and cost-effective manner. And also, it is aimed to design a fully automatic system that assists the operators in obtaining the standard accuracy rate. The flow diagram of the current study focusing on the separation and counting of immature white blood cells in the blood from other elements is presented in **Figure 1**.

Methodology. *In the present study, it is planned to distinguish ALL patients from healthy individuals. For this purpose, analyzes are made on the microscopic images of peripheral blood samples obtained from the website <https://homes.di.unimi.it/scotti/all/>. All images in the public and free ALL-IDB dataset are captured at different magnifications and densities using the Canon PowerShot G5 camera. Assessments are provided using images from the ALL-DIB 1+ALL-IDB2 datasets.*

YOLO (You Only Look Once) Approach

YOLO is a deep learning network that detects and classifies blast cells in blood samples captured by the microscope. The inputs given to the algorithm are the data obtained with different magnification rates from areas with varied densities of blood elements. Version 4 of Yolo is preferred for accurate distinguishing and counting of blast cells segmented on these data.

Figure 1. Flow chart of the presented study

The YOLOV4 algorithm developed by is an enhanced version of YOLOV3. The backbone part is the CSPDarknet53 structure, in which CSPNet and Darknet53 architectures are used together. This structure which plays a role in feature extraction reduces computation and memory costs and improves the learning ability of CNN. The neck part of the YOLOV4 algorithm consists of SPP and PAN approaches and the head part consists of the YOLOV3 algorithm.

SPP is a module that improves the receptive field and consists of Spatial Pyramid Matching (SPM). SPM (Spatial Pyramid Matching) divides the input image as SXS into a grid to obtain the spatial pyramid. It is then integrated into CNN by SPP. The PAN structure is used to collect parameters from different backbone levels.

YOLOV4 being a one-step method produces output by calculating the coordinates and category probability of the given input. The target detection process is presented in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Target detection process for YOLOv4 algorithm.

The YOLO algorithm, in which the image is considered as a whole, separates the data into SXS coordinates. It estimates the bounding box coordinates for the relevant object in the image and evaluates the probability that the object in these boxes is a blast cell. The probability of whether a blast cell is present or not is available for all grids, and aspect ratios are estimated based on the entire image.

The rates of loss value obtained as a result of the training performed on the ALL-IDB 1+ALL-IDB2 datasets with the YOLOV4 algorithm are presented in **Figure3**.

Figure 3. Detection and counting process on ALL-IDB 1+ALL-IDB2 dataset

Table1: A comparison on studies using the ALL-IDB dataset

A comparison on studies using the ALL-IDB dataset				
Author	Aim of study	Method	Dataset	Results
<i>Jha, K. K. & Dutta, H. S. 2019</i>	<i>Leukaemia detection modul from the blood smear images</i>	<i>MI+LDP+SCA based deep CN classifier</i>	<i>ALL-IDB2</i>	<i>Accuracy is % 98,7</i>
<i>Al-jaboriy, S.S. Sjarif, N.N. A. Chuprat, S. & Abdullallah, W. M.</i>	<i>To develop a new and improved technique for leukocyte cell segmentation</i>	<i>GA+ANN</i>	<i>ALL-IDB1</i>	<i>Identified blast cell accuracy is %97</i>
<i>Al-Tahhan, F.E. Fares, M.E. Sakr, A.A. & Aladle, D.A. 2020.</i>	<i>To identify automatically the ALL subtypest (L1/L2/L3)</i>	<i>KNN/SVM/ANN</i>	<i>ALL-IDB2</i>	<i>Maximum accuracy is obtained as % 100 by quadratic SVM</i>
<i>Safuan, S.N. M. Tomari, M.R.M. Zakaria, W.N.W. Mohd, M.N.H. & Suriani, N.S. 2020.</i>	<i>To differentiate lymphoblast and non-lymphoblast cells and examine ALL disease</i>	<i>VGG/GoogleNet/Alexnet</i>	<i>ALL-IDB2 (60 images)</i>	<i>Maximum accuracy is obtained as % 99,13 by VGG</i>
<i>Sahlol, A.T. Kollmannsberger P. & Ewees, A.A. 2020</i>	<i>White blood cell leukaemia image classification</i>	<i>SESSA+VGGNet</i>	<i>ALL-IDB2</i>	<i>Accuracy is % 96,11</i>
<i>Anilkumar, K.K. Manoj, V.J. & Sagi, T.M. 2021.</i>	<i>Automated identification of leukaemia</i>	<i>Transfer Learning Architectures</i>	<i>ALL-IDB1 ALL-IDB2</i>	<i>Maximum accuracy is % 100 both ALL-D-IDB1 and ALL-IDB2 dataset</i>

This study aims to evaluate ALL disease using the peripheral blood smear technique. As a result of the study, the output will be produced in 3–4 seconds with real-time automatic diagnosis provided on digitized peripheral blood smear images. With this study on the identification and counting of blast cells from hundreds of cells, the severity of the disease will be evaluated, the right treatment protocol will be selected and the response to the treatment will be monitored. It is expected that this study will provide helpful ideas to physicians.

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